

Development Of Wurung Crater Tourism Object In Increasing Regional Original Income In Bondowoso Regency, East Java

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Abstract

Regional Original Revenue which is a description of the regional financial potential that controls the elements of regional taxes and levies. The government realizes that the tourism sector is not the largest contributor to regional income, but has the potential to increase Regional Original Income (PAD). The purpose of the study was to determine the efforts made by the local government of Bondowoso Regency in developing the Wurung crater tourism object and the factors that encourage and hinder the development of its potential. The method used is a qualitative approach. The focus of this research is the efforts made by the Bondowoso Regency Government in developing the Wurung Crater tourism object and the factors that encourage and hinder the development of its potential. The results of the study indicate that the factors that encourage the development of the Wurung Crater tourism object is the attractiveness it has and is supported by adequate facilities and infrastructure. Efforts made by the Department of Tourism, Youth and Sports to organize the location of the Wurung Crater, overcome the damage that occurred, provide counseling to all parties that affect the development of tourism.

Keywords: local revenue; wurung crater

A. Introduction

The implementation of regional development is basically an integral part of national development which is directed at developing regions and harmonizing growth rates between regions in Indonesia. In regional development, of course, it is necessary to increase the utilization of regional potential optimally. Law no. 32 of 2004 concerning Regional Government is one of the juridical foundations for the development of regional autonomy in Indonesia. In this Law it is stated that in the context of administering regional government in accordance with the mandate of the 1945 Constitution, regional governments that regulate and manage government affairs themselves according to the principles of autonomy and co-administration are directed at accelerating the realization of social welfare through improvement, service, empowerment, and community participation, as well as increasing regional competitiveness by taking into account the principles of democracy, equity, justice, privileges and specificity of a region within the system of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia.

The autonomy given to the Regency and City regions is carried out by giving the widest, real, and accountable authority to the regional government in a proportional manner. Thus, the

delegation of responsibilities will be followed by arrangements for the distribution and utilization of national resources in an equitable manner, as well as the balance of central and regional finances. In managing and managing their own households, of course the regions require substantial funds to finance the administration of governance and development in the regions. Therefore the regions are given the right and authority to explore their own regional revenue sources (PAD). This is in accordance with the provisions of article 157UU No. 32 of 2004 which regulates regional revenue sources.

PAD which is an illustration of regional financial potential generally relies on elements of regional taxes and regional levies. With regard to regional own-source revenue from the retribution sector, regions can explore the potential of natural resources in the form of tourism objects. The government is aware that the tourism sector is not the largest contributor to regional income, but has the potential to increase PAD. Fortunately, Indonesia still has natural potential. and quite large cultural arts that can be utilized by the region to increase local revenue.

In the current era of globalization, tourism is one of the activities that has a very strategic role in supporting the development of the national economy. Apart from being a reliable source of foreign exchange earners, this sector is also a sector capable of absorbing labor and encouraging investment development. To develop this sector, the government is trying hard to make plans and various policies that support the direction of progress in this sector. One of these policies is to explore, inventory and develop existing tourist objects as the main attractions for tourists.

Tourism has an important role in national development, namely as a foreign exchange earner, equalizing and increasing employment and income opportunities, strengthening unity and integrity, and getting to know the nation's culture. As mandated in the 1999 Outlines of State Policy (GBHN), that developing tourism, through a complete and integrated system approach is interdisciplinary and participatory using economic, technical, agronomic, socio-cultural, energy saving, preserving nature and not damage the environment. (TAP MPR No.IV/MPR/1999).

B. Methods

The research method is using qualitative descriptive which is given the existing tourism objects and their potential which is quite rapid in the future. Of the several tourist objects in Bondowoso Regency, the Wurung Crater tourist attraction is a tourist park which has various

features such as its very beautiful natural scenery. The Wurung crater tourism object is expected to be able to make a sizable contribution to Bondowoso Regency's PAD.

C. Results and Discussion

1. Regional Revenue Sources

Regional income includes all receipts of money through regional treasury accounts, which add to equity funds, are regional rights within one fiscal year and do not need to be repaid by the regions.

Regional income is grouped into:

a. Regional Original Income (PAD) which consists of:

1) Regional tax results

Regional taxes are broken down by object of income in accordance with the law on regional taxes

2) Regional levies

Regional levies are broken down by object of income in accordance with the law on regional levies

3) Results of separated regional wealth management

What is meant by the results of regional wealth management that are separated include, among others, the share of profits from BUMD, the results of cooperation with third parties

4) Other valid Regional Original Revenues include regional revenues outside of regional taxes and levies such as giro services, proceeds from the sale of regional assets.

b. Balancing Fund

Balancing funds are funds sourced from the APBN allocated to regions to fund regional needs in the implementation of decentralization.

c. Other legal regional income

What is meant by "other legitimate regional revenues" includes grants or emergency funds from the government

2. Main Duties and Functions of the Bondowoso Tourism, Youth and Sports Service

Based on Bondowoso Regent Regulation Number 83 of 2016 Chapter III article 5, Disparpora has the task of carrying out government affairs which are the authority of the region in the Tourism Sector and the Youth and Sports Sector. In carrying out its duties, Disparpora has the following functions:

- a. Formulation of technical policies in the context of planning, fostering and developing tourism, youth and sports;
 - b. Providing support for the implementation of regional government in the tourism, youth and sports sectors;
 - c. Implementation of operational policies, provision of guidance and coaching, granting of permits;
 - d. Monitoring, supervision and control in planning activities in the tourism, youth and sports sectors;
 - e. Monitoring, supervising and controlling the implementation of the main tasks;
 - f. Formulation and management of district tourism strategic areas;
 - g. Management and development of district tourism destinations;
 - h. Issuance of recommendations for the management of district tourism business registration certificates;
 - i. Development of tourism human resources, arts and creative economy;
 - j. Marketing of regency tourism products and destinations;
 - k. Facilitating spaces for expression, promotion and interaction for creative people in the district;
 - l. Recruitment, empowerment and development of pioneer youth, budding young entrepreneurs and district youth cadres;
 - m. Fostering and developing youth organizations as well as traditional/recreational sports;
 - n. Planning for improving youth and sports facilities and infrastructure;
 - o. Development of traditional sports and recreation;
 - p. Preparation of financial reports which include budget realization reports, balance sheets and notes on financial reports, office supplies and equipment; and Implementation of other official duties given by the Regent in accordance with the duties and functions.
- 3. Efforts made by the Regional Government of Bondowoso Regency in developing the Wurung Crater tourism object**

The Wurung Crater tourism object is one of the tourism objects managed by the Bondowoso Regency government. So that the development of the tourism object itself is the responsibility of the Bondowoso Regency government which in this case is the Bondowoso Regency Tourism, Youth and Sports Service (DISPARPORA).

Efforts to implement the development/provision of tourism facilities and environmental management in Bondowoso Regency are directed towards the following:

1. Increasing the development of tourism facilities and infrastructure

2. Development of superior tour types and packages
 3. Monitoring and evaluating the implementation of tourism marketing destination development programs
 4. Development, outreach, and implementation and supervision of standardization
- Referring to the policy directions above, the targets of tourism development activities in Bondowoso Regency are as follows:

1. Realization of increased development of tourism facilities and infrastructure
2. Implementation of the development of types and superior tour packages
3. Implementation of monitoring and evaluation of the implementation of tourism marketing destination development programs
4. Implementation of development, socialization, and implementation and supervision of standardization

In order for this target to be achieved, the program taken is:

1. Increased dissemination/dissemination of information on tourism potential and tourism promotion cooperation
2. Increasing tourism destination infrastructure
3. Improving the quality of human resources in the field of tourism

In developing the Wurung Crater tourism object itself, the Tourism, Youth and Sports Office of Bondowoso Regency has several future programs, including:

1. Carry out promotions through booklets/leaflets, participating in exhibitions, print media, electronic media, internet as well as performances at local and regional levels
2. Carry out Organization of Interesting Tourism and Cultural Events for Tourists
3. Improving tourism management human resources through Tourism Awareness Group (POKDARWIS) training, training for integrated Bondowoso traditional arts groups, training for tour guides (guides) and coaching groups in the tourism sector
4. Improving tourism object management facilities and infrastructure including:
 - a. Construction of a parking area in the tourist area of Wurung crater
 - b. Construction of steps in the tourist area of the Wurung crater
 - c. Construction of the gate / entrance to the Wurung crater area
 - d. Construction of warehouses / warehouses for storing tourism equipment and supplies

Meanwhile, programs from the Department of Tourism, Youth and Sports to develop Wurung Crater tourism objects that have been implemented include:

1. : Implementation of promotions with several indicators:
 - a. Availability of 5000 copies of travel booklets, 5000 copies of travel leaflets
 - b. The creation of a tourism magazine
 - c. Implementation of the Bondowoso E-Tourism application
 - d. Implementation of Bondowoso tourism publication (National Newspaper)
 - e. Implementation of tourism publications Bondowoso (TV)
 - f. Production of tourism promotion videos
 - g. Implementation of making the DISPARPORA Website
 2. Realization of organizing tourism and cultural events that are attractive to tourists by:
 - a. Implementation of Fam Trip Travel Agent
 - b. Implementation of a tourism roadshow
 - c. tourism and creative economy exhibition at the Muharram Festival
 - d. performance of the Bondowoso Ijen Festival
 3. Participation in every local, regional and national level event including:
 - a. District participation. Bondowoso in the Nusantara Tourism Award (AWN) - East Java
 - b. Participate in promotions at the Majapahit Travel Fair (MTF)
 - c. Implementation of a tourism roadshow
 4. Development of tourism facilities and infrastructure, namely:
 - a. The writing of Wurung Crater was carried out
 - b. Implementation of the construction of shelters, gazebos and viewing posts (Wurung Crater)
 - c. Implementation of the construction of children's play facilities (Wurung Crater)
 - d. The construction of a rest house (Wurung Crater) was completed
 - e. Procurement of ATVs (Wurung Crater)
 - f. Implementation of the procurement of MTB bicycles (Wurung Crater)
Procurement of tents (Wrung Crater)
 5. To improve the human resources of tourism managers, the realization of Tourism Awareness Group (POKDARWIS) training, training for integrated Bondowoso traditional arts groups, training for tour guides, training for tour guides (guide) and coaching groups in the tourism sector.
- 4. Factors That Encourage and Hinder the Development of the Wurung Crater Tourism Object**

a. Factors Encouraging the Development of Wurung Crater Tourism Objects

Based on the research results obtained from direct observation, interviews, and documents at the Wurung Crater tourist attraction, the researchers identified the results of an assessment of the tourism potential.

1) Attractiveness

The main attractions in the Wurung Crater object are:

- a) Stunning panoramic beauty of the plantation area and pine forests during the trip
- b) The natural landscape of the crater and green savanna meadows is like a wide and green carpet with a depression shaped like a mountain crater, some say that Wurung Crater is a miniature of Mount Bromo, some are reminiscent of savanna like in New Zealand, the landscape is also mentioned like the Teletubbies movie
- c) The weather is cool and cold because of its position at an altitude of 1500 meters above sea level, plus the natural feel of the trees
- d) Can carry out tourism activities such as Gowes around Wurung Crater by bicycle, ATV etc
- e) It is suitable to be used as an off road sports location
- f) the place is very wide and the scenery is charming to be a plus point for doing outdoor activities
- g) Become a place to practice paragliding and hang gliding

2) Means of Transportation

The road to the location of the Wurung Crater tourist attraction does not need to be confused because there are already directions along the way and the road conditions are quite good compared to before, which previously could only be passed by off-road vehicles, now other vehicles can pass it, although there are some roads that are narrow. it is still uneven but does not affect the speed of the vehicle and can even be passed by a family car so that not a few tourists who visit the Wurung crater object have a picnic with their family and sit back and enjoy the very beautiful natural panorama.

3) Management, maintenance and service

In terms of management, maintenance and service, this tourism object is managed by the Department of Tourism, Youth and Sports (Diparpora) which is operationally managed by Perum Perhutani, Bondowoso Regency. Good service and hospitality and responsiveness from the manager is one of the important factors in tourism, because with this good service tourists who visit will feel comfortable and safe. Service at the

location for tourists is quite good because there are officers appointed for cleaning and guiding tourists who need explanations or assistance Akomodasi

Accommodation is available at the Wurung crater tourist attraction in the form of a place to sit and relax enjoying the natural beauty of the Wurung crater and a resting place for tourists. Tents are provided for tourists who want to stay overnight to enjoy the beauty and atmosphere of the Wurung crater at night.

4) Facilities and Infrastructure

Facilities and infrastructure in tourism objects include toll gates and ticket booths, parking lots, toilets/ bathrooms, prayer rooms, writings on Wurung Crater, shelters, gazebos and viewing posts, children's games, rest houses, ATVs, MTB bicycles, tents.

The facilities available at the Wurung crater tourism object are not optimal because they require quite expensive costs to repair and to provide them. The water in the Wurung Kawh tourism object also still comes from water delivery because there is no water source at the Wurung crater location. The use of water is mainly for tourists' toilet needs. In addition, the availability of water in the tourist area of Wurung Crater is also to meet the needs of clean water for tourists who need it.

b. Factors that Obstacle the Development of the Wurung Crater Tourism Object

From the results of the interview according to Mr. Arif Setyo Rahardjo, SST. Par as Head of ODTW and Tourism Service Business on October 20 2017 there are several factors that hinder the development of tourism objects as follows:

1) Internal factors, namely:

- a) Inadequate facilities and infrastructure (construction of parking areas, gates/entrances and tourist equipment storage buildings)
- b) The quality and quantity of human resources in the tourism sector is still lacking
- c) The awareness of some tourism service entrepreneurs and the public is still low
- d) There is still land that has not been utilized for tourism development
- e) Less beautiful tourist objects because of inappropriate tourism arrangements
- f) There is still limited infrastructure funding in the region
- g) Declining community pride in their own region

2) External factors, namely:

- a) The rise of tourism development in other areas outside Bondowoso Regency

- b) The increasing influence of external culture that influences, thus causing the weakening of regional culture
- c) Many visitors do not heed local regulations (local cultural wisdom) so that local people feel less enthusiastic about maintaining local cultural wisdom
- d) people who do not support the accelerated development of tourist objects and attractions
- e) people who do not support the accelerated development of tourist objects and attractions

5. Tourism Potential of Wurung Crater and Its Impact on Bondowoso PAD

Regional Revenue and Expenditure Budget, hereinafter referred to as APBD, is the annual regional government financial plan that is discussed and approved jointly by the Regional Government and the Regional People's Representative Council, and is stipulated by regional regulations. The Regional Revenue and Expenditure Budget consists of a revenue budget, expenditure budget, and financing budget.

Regional revenues for Bondowoso Regency come from the remainder of the previous year's budget, Regional Original Revenue (PAD), the balance fund portion, the regional loan portion, and other legitimate revenue portions. The regional expenditures of Bondowoso Regency consist of routine expenditures and development expenditures.

Local Own Revenue, hereinafter referred to as PAD, is income obtained by a region that is collected based on regional regulations in accordance with statutory regulations. Regional Own Revenue is sourced from regional taxes, regional levies, separated regional wealth management results, and other legitimate regional original revenues.

From the results of the research above, it can be seen that the development of the Wurung Crater tourism object has the potential to support Bondowoso District Original Revenue, although not too large. The contribution of Wurung Crater to Regional Original Revenue is an average of 105.03% or an average of IDR 12,531,046. Parking fees on average increased by 187.82%. or an average of IDR 25,806,667.-. This was supported by an increase in the amount of tourism object levy fees for Wurung Crater on deposits III and IV, which increased by 32.06% and 37.93% or Rp. 3,377,640 and Rp. 6,438,800, - according to existing data.

The tourism object income for Wurung Crater listed in table 3 is the income at the Office of Tourism, Youth and Sports received from profit sharing with Perum Perhutani, the distribution of which is Wurung Crater's income after deducting expenses with a percentage of 60% Perum Perhutani with details of 55% revenue sharing 5% monitoring and evaluation costs,

for a percentage of 40% Tourism, Youth and Sports Office with details of 35% revenue sharing 5% monitoring and evaluation costs

However, levy income from the Wurung Crater tourism object is strongly influenced by the number of visitors. The greater the number of visitors to a tourist attraction, the greater the levy income from the object will be. Therefore, the size of the efforts made by the manager of these attractions is very influential in attracting tourists. In this case, the tourism object manager must be able to package the tourism object in such a way that it is suitable for sale.

The driving factor in the development of the Wurung Crater tourist attraction which consists of the stunning panoramic beauty of the plantation area and pine forests during the trip, the natural landscape of the crater and green savanna meadows like a carpet that stretches wide and green with a niche shaped like a mountain crater, some say Wurung Crater is a miniature of Mount Bromo, some are reminiscent of savanna like in New Zealand, the landscape is also mentioned like the Teletubbies movie, the weather is cool and cold because of its position at an altitude of 1500 meters above sea level, plus the natural feel of trees, can carry out tourist activities such as Riding around the Wurung Crater by bicycle, ATV, is very suitable to be used as an off road sports location, the place is very wide and the charming scenery is an added point for carrying out outdoor activities, as a place to practice paragliding and hang gliding.

When examined from the theory put forward by Salah Wahab (2003: 110) the development of Wurung Crater tourism objects is in accordance with the theory, some are not appropriate. What is appropriate, for example, is the layout of the land and the natural landscape of the crater and green savanna meadows like a wide and green carpet, sufficient sunlight, and clean air free from pollution. There is an enchanting natural phenomenon, namely mountains with beautiful panoramas surrounded by a giant hole like a keldera, some say that the Wurung Crater is a miniature of Mount Bromo, some are reminiscent of savanna like in New Zealand, the landscape is also mentioned like the Teletubbies movie, besides that there is a view of the grasslands in the middle of the Wurung Crater and the flower fields across from the crater

During the trip, you will be presented with natural nuances of trees, pine forests and side by side coffee plantations. After that, you can see on the right and left of the road, the view of our eyes will not turn away from the sweetness of the flower fields. The work of humans in the tourist area of Wurung Crater, namely the writing of Wurung Crater which looks like Hollywood writing in America adds its own charm as well as a medium for taking pictures. Wurung Crater is also equipped with a viewing tower so that tourists can see beauty

D. Conclusion

Based on the results of research, data analysis, and discussion of the results of research on the Development of Wurung Crater Tourism Objects in Increasing Regional Original Income (PAD), the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. The efforts made by the management, namely the Bondowoso Regency Tourism, Youth and Sports Service (Disparpora) to develop Wurung Crater tourism objects are:
 - a. To overcome the lack of arrangement of the location of the Wurung Crater and there is still land that has not been utilized for tourism development
 - b. To overcome the damage, the Department of Tourism, Youth and Sports (Disparpora) built awareness of tourism service business entrepreneurs and the community
 - c. Providing counseling to the community and tourism service businesses so that they have concern and a sense of belonging to the Wurung Crater tourism object
 - d. To improve human resources, the Tourism, Youth and Sports (Disparpora) agency provides training and tourism development
2. Factors that encourage the development of Wurung Crater tourism objects include: the attractiveness of Wurung Crater, good communication facilities, management by the Department of Tourism, Youth and Sports (Disparpora), good accommodation and good tourist infrastructure. adequate. While the inhibiting factors consist of the lack of arrangement of the location of the Wurung Crater and there is still land that has not been utilized for tourism development, a lack of concern from the community and tourism service business actors and a professional workforce.
3. The contribution from the Wurung Crater tourism object to local revenue is still small, although it almost always increases

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